

TRAINING, RETRAINING AND ADVANCED TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS IN THE SYSTEM OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES DURING THE PERIOD OF REFORMS OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the issues of training, retraining, and advanced training of specialists in the system of internal affairs bodies during the reforms of New Uzbekistan. It examines the role of the modern education system in enhancing the professional potential of internal affairs officers, the legal and institutional foundations of educational processes, as well as new approaches within the framework of reforms. The article analyzes the use of foreign experience, innovative technologies, and educational methods in training specialists. At the same time, proposals were made to increase the effectiveness of personnel training and ensure their compliance with modern requirements.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, training, retraining, advanced training of specialists, New Uzbekistan, reforms, vocational education, innovative technologies, legal framework, personnel policy, effectiveness.

It is no exaggeration to say that one of the main directions of the reforms being carried out in our country in the current period of reforms in New Uzbekistan, or in other words, in the period of the Third Renaissance, is the identification and elimination of the conditions that contributed to the causes and emergence of offenses, as well as increasing the effectiveness of the crime prevention system, raising the legal culture and awareness of citizens, and forming in them a spirit of observance of the rules of conduct established in society. The implementation of these tasks is one of the urgent tasks assigned to law enforcement agencies, and in the effective implementation of these tasks, internal affairs bodies play an important role in the system of law enforcement agencies.

In the implementation of these tasks, special attention should be paid to the training, retraining, and advanced training of specialists in the system of internal affairs bodies, which is one of the important and necessary requirements of today.

It can be said that in recent years, a significant part of the state budget expenditures has been directed towards the accelerated development of social infrastructure facilities in the republic. In particular, funds from the state budget are allocated for the development of education and science.

It should be noted that today education has become the most priority area of state policy. Funds allocated from the state budget for education constitute a significant portion of budget expenditures. In particular, construction, major reconstruction, and repair work has been carried out in almost all public education institutions operating in our country. Great attention is paid to the quality and content of education in educational institutions, equipped with modern educational laboratories and furniture. In particular, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the processes of these reforms directly encompass the system of training, retraining, and advanced training of specialists within the system of law enforcement agencies.

In particular, in order to ensure public safety in the country, form an integrated system for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, establish the effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the republican level, strengthen law and order and legality, ensure peace and tranquility of the population through the introduction of modern working methods, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level"[\[1\]](#) was adopted, defining the following as fundamentally new mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies:

- solving problems related to crime prevention and combating crime directly on the ground by identifying and eliminating the causes of crime in the context of each mahalla, family, and individual;
- categorization of each district, city, and mahalla, based on the state of crime in the regions, and involvement of all necessary forces and means to eliminate "hotbeds of crime" in cooperation with khokimiyats, sectors, and the public;
- ensuring peace and stability in our country through the introduction of integrated management and continuous control mechanisms based on the "republic - region - district - mahalla" system, effective coordination of the activities of internal affairs bodies and other state bodies to ensure public safety;
- creating a modern image of internal affairs officers, increasing their responsibility and professional potential, forming the necessary skills to combat new forms of crime, and achieving full digitalization of the sphere.

At the same time, in order to ensure the implementation of this Decree, on April 2, 2021, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5050 "On Additional Organizational Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime"[\[2\]](#) was adopted. The "Concept for Organizing Spiritual and Educational Work in Internal Affairs Bodies" was approved by this resolution, and it was determined that the work to enhance the spiritual and intellectual potential of internal affairs officers will be organized based on the conceptual idea "Serving the Motherland and the people faithfully is our highest duty!"

Also, in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level," the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 15, 2021 No. PP-5076 "On Measures to Introduce a Qualitatively New System for Training Professional Personnel for Internal Affairs Bodies"[\[3\]](#) was adopted, according to which, in order to introduce a fundamentally new system for training specialists for internal affairs bodies, ensure career growth of employees depending on their qualifications, as well as further enhance the intellectual and professional potential of managerial personnel in the effective management of forces and resources:

Starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, a two-stage higher education system, including bachelor's and master's degrees, has been introduced into the personnel training process at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the task has been set to qualitatively implement a two-stage higher education system, organize the educational process based on the most modern pedagogical and information technologies, and enhance

the scientific and pedagogical potential of the teaching staff, including through their training in foreign educational institutions.

At the same time, based on this resolution, the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs was granted the status of a legal entity, and the following were defined as the main areas of its activity:

- special professional training of sergeant personnel in the field of organizing activities to ensure public safety in all areas of sectoral services of internal affairs bodies;
- training of employees appointed for the first time to positions of rank-and-file and officer corps of internal affairs bodies based on training programs for initial professional training;
- organization of retraining and advanced training of all categories of employees of internal affairs bodies using innovative information and pedagogical technologies, including on the basis of republican higher educational institutions of related fields.
- Implementation of the practice of conducting distance and mobile field courses to ensure the advanced training of internal affairs officers directly on-site without interruption from service.

Also, from September 1, 2021, a system of continuous educational and career processes will be introduced into the procedure for serving in the internal affairs bodies, and for appointment to the relevant positions of the leading personnel of the internal affairs bodies, it is mandatory to study in the Academy's master's programs in the specialties "Organizational and Tactical Management" and "Organizational and Strategic Management," as well as the requirement for employees to undergo retraining and advanced training courses as one of the main requirements for assigning special ranks and appointing employees of the rank-and-file and sergeant ranks to officer positions, and only persons with higher education will be accepted for service in sergeant positions of the internal affairs bodies, and candidates for rank-and-file positions of the internal affairs bodies will be accepted only from among graduates of departmental academic lyceums, military-academic lyceums, assistants to prevention inspectors, as well as persons with higher education or studying in a correspondence form of education.

Another regulatory legal act adopted in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. UP-6196 "On Measures to Raise the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Field of Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a Qualitatively New Level" is the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 15, 2021 No. PP-5077 "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Training Professional Personnel in the Field of Ensuring Public [Safety](#)"[4].

In accordance with this resolution, the Military-Technical Institute of the National Guard has been transformed into the University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has been designated as a basic higher military educational and research institution for the targeted training of qualified personnel in the following areas:

- for the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Guard - in the areas of ensuring public safety, respectively, the protection of public order, road safety, and the implementation of the requirements of the passport system;
- For the Armed Forces and other law enforcement agencies - in the field of military diplomacy, jurisprudence and economics, as well as engineering-technical, educational-psychological and command-tactical activities;

- for state and economic management bodies that have their own security structures - in all areas of organization and implementation of security activities.

In conclusion, one of the main tasks is the protection of human rights and freedoms and legitimate interests in society, the protection of public order and ensuring public safety, the fight against offenses and, in general, the prevention of offenses, the identification and elimination of their causes and conditions contributing to their commission, the identification of persons prone to committing offenses, the training, retraining and advanced training of specialists in the system of law enforcement agencies in raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, and their further activities are of great importance in ensuring normal, peaceful, and tranquil life in the social life of society.

References:

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